
Water Pollution and Human Health

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Abstract:

Water is the most vital element among the natural resources, and is critical for the survival of all living organisms including human, food production, and economic development. In present scenario we cannot say water is life instead we should say unpolluted water is life polluted water led to death only. Life is not possible without the water. Human being cannot live without the water. For a healthy life pure and pollution free water is indispensable. In India water pollution is a major problem and in recent years due to industrialization and urbanization, this problem has taken a gigantic shape. Though not mentioned in Indian constitution, but like right to life, right to access water is a basic human right. Life of a human cannot be sustained with polluted water. Pollution free water is the only hope for the healthy life. The root cause of a number of diseases is the polluted water. There are a number of causes responsible for pollution of the water as polluted water doesn't come from a single source. One cannot imagine how unknowingly we invite a number of diseases due to Polluted water. As the effect of polluted water remains for a long time, so it not only affects the life of present generation but it also affects the life of upcoming generations. Nearly 40000 persons have consumed this contaminated water over the past 14 to 20 years and cancers, birth defects and diseases related to skin, lungs, brain, kidneys and liver are several times more prevalent in that community than anywhere else in the country. In recent years, water pollution has become a serious problem across the country, mostly due to the

presence of untreated effluents, chemicals and pesticides in it.

Keywords: unpolluted, indispensable, access, gigantic, responsible, contaminated, consumed, effluents, pesticides.

Introduction

Pollution of water is a great and growing threat to global health. Water pollution occurs when harmful substances like chemicals or microorganisms—contaminate a stream, river, lake, ocean, aquifer, or other body of water, degrading water quality and rendering it toxic for the human beings or the environment. The quality of drinking water is an essential factor affecting human health. In present scenario we cannot say water is life instead we should say unpolluted water is life polluted water lead to death only. Life is not possible without the water. Human being cannot live without the water. For a healthy life pure and pollution free water is indispensable. In India water pollution is a major problem and in recent years due to industrialization and urbanization, this problem has taken a gigantic shape. There are many causes of water pollution. These causes can be removed or at least controlled with the awareness amongst the people and by the strong implementation of the legislative measures. Only about 10% of the waste water generated is treated; the rest is discharged as it is into our water bodies. Due to this, pollutants enter into groundwater, rivers and other water bodies, puts serious effect on human body causing many fatal diseases. We can divide the causes of water pollution into two parts one is direct and the second is indirect. The quality of drinking water in developing countries is worrying. The negative health effects of water pollution remain the leading cause of morbidity and mortality in developing countries. Water is fundamental to human existence, but in a polluted or contaminated ecological state it may pose a health hazard. Water resources have been extensively

managed, or environmentally altered, used and reused, for all kinds of economic reasons, such as drinking, food production, flood control, energy, industry, nature, and recreation, with subsequent effects on water quantity and quality.

Water is uniquely vulnerable to pollution. Known as a “universal solvent,” water is able to dissolve more substances than any other liquid on earth. Pollutants in water means the presence of various toxics include a wide spectrum of chemicals, pathogens and physical chemistry or sensory changes. Used water is wastewater. It comes from our sinks, showers, and toilets and from commercial, industrial, and agricultural activities. Industry is the main cause of water pollution, these industries include distillery industry, tannery industry, pulp and paper industry, textile industry, food industry, iron and steel industry, nuclear industry and so on. water pollution results from both human and natural factors. Various human activities will directly affect water quality, including urbanization, population growth, industrial production, climate change, and other factors (Halder,54) Moreover, water gets polluted when contaminants—from pesticides and fertilizers to waste leached from landfills and septic systems—make their way into an aquifer, rendering it unsafe for human use. Wastes are most often discharged into the receiving water bodies with little or no regard to their assimilative capacities. The discharge of raw sewage, garbage, as well as oil spills are threats to the diluting capabilities of the lagoons and rivers in the major cities.

Water quality issues are a major challenge that humanity is facing in the twenty-first century.

Water has multifunctional roles in our daily life. It is used for every chore of our life like drinking, bathing, cleaning and irrigation etc. The main sources of water are lakes, rivers, oceans, ponds and groundwater. State also provides water to the people Lack of water and sanitation services also increases the incidence of diseases such as cholera, trachoma, schistosomiasis, and helminthiasis. Data from

studies in developing countries show a clear relationship between cholera and contaminated water, and household water treatment and storage can reduce cholera (Gundry,94) The impact of water pollution on human health is significant, although there may be regional, age, gender, and other differences in degree. The most common disease caused by water pollution is diarrhea, which is mainly transmitted by enteroviruses in the aquatic environment. A large proportion of these are caused by exposure to microbially infected water and food, and diarrhea in infants and young children can lead to malnutrition and reduced immune resistance, thereby increasing the likelihood of prolonged and recurrent diarrhea (Marino,213)

As most of these activities lead to water contamination with diverse synthetic and geogenic natural chemicals, it comes as no surprise that chemical pollution of natural water has become a major public concern in almost all parts of the world. More than 80% of sewage generated by human activities is discharged into rivers and oceans without any treatment, Some aspects of waterborne diseases and the urgent need for improved sanitation in developing countries are also discussed. These problems are going to be more aggravated in the future by climate change, resulting in higher water temperatures, melting of glaciers, and an intensification of the water cycle. People (swimmers and non-swimmers) exposed to waters above threshold levels of bacteria had a higher relative risk of developing skin disease, and levels of bacteria in swimmers are 3.5 times more likely to report skin diseases than non- swimmers. It is also possible seawater were highly correlated with skin symptoms. Studies have also suggested that that swimmer exaggerated their symptoms, reporting conditions that others would not classify as true skin disorders (Fleisher,154)

We're all accountable to some degree for today's water pollution problem. Fortunately, there are some simple ways you can prevent water contamination or at least limit your contribution to it like by properly disposing of chemical cleaners, oils, and nonbiodegradable

items to keep them from going down the drain. Governments should strengthen water intervention management and carry out intervention measures to improve water quality and reduce water pollution's impact on human health. It is necessary to study the impact of water pollution on human health, especially disease heterogeneity, and clarify the importance of clean drinking water, which has important theoretical and practical significance for realizing sustainable development goals.

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